

Assessing the Role of Mining Safety and Health Regulations in Monitoring and Maintaining Slope Stability in the Kenyan and Ghanaian Mines

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ABSTRACT

The open-air excavation of construction rocks and valuable minerals and the consequences of un-optimized overall slope angles and quarrying designs on slope stability and sustainable mining in Kenyan and Ghanaian opencast mines insist on the critical role of legislative frameworks for the mining sectors in mining mine slope stability assessment maintenance. The stability conditions of the slopes of the mines were assessed using the Limit Equilibrium numerical analysis technique, and geospatial statistics and applied Artificial Intelligence [AI] tools to assess the slopes' compliance with mining rules and regulations in both countries. The applied approach integrates field observations and measurements of sampled geometry parameters of the quarry to determine mechanical parameters and a well-defined numerical modeling calculus using slide 6.0 slope stability analysis software. The Limit Equilibrium numerical analysis indicates a large influence on scale plans and overall slope angles of the excavated quarries in relation to other limiting factors. The other results identify that the mining regulations in the Mining Act Chapter 306, 2019 of Kenya and the Minerals and Mining Act 2006 Act 703 of Ghana are critical in ensuring safety and health for the mining operations for sustainable development. Applied Artificial Intelligence helps rank the regulations based on the implementation, application, and sustainability of the mining sector.

Keywords: Artisanal mining, Slope stability, Limit equilibrium method, Slope stabilization, Sustainable mining, Mining regulations, Artificial Intelligence

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In most quarrying areas worldwide, frequent slope instability and failures are prone to natural factors or other factors, causing low economic standards [6]. Rock slopes collapsing can be classified based on type and structural control levels. The most common types include planar, wedge, toppling, and circular collapses. The major internal factors that affect the stability of a rock slope are the rock slope's geometric conformity, the features of its possible failure planes, surface drainage, and groundwater conditions [24]. The majority of minerals processed and produced globally are open-pit mined. Open-cast mining is characterized by its high degree of mechanization and high production rates, making it an efficient mining method. Open casten mining rock is done depending on the stabilities and the gradients since the rock should not fail at one point before completing the mine life [10]. It is depicted that the output of different minerals has significantly accelerated due to rapid growth in open-cast mining activities and a

high level of mechanization. Amount of the waste mining and dumping is dependent on the area, which in turn leads to slope instability and quarry slopes collapse, opening the resultant quarry [16]. Due to the clustered characteristic of most of the production areas at the pick and close to the excavation floor level, there can be a catastrophic loss of life and property with the worsen dangers that can haunt the workers and the equipment being operated. It is doomed if a slope collapses in an open-pit mine since the collapse sizes range from a few meters to gigantic and directly affect workers, machinery, and the methods of finishing a production line [11]. There is a need to study and calculate slope stability to see how to control the calamities [5].

Slope failures of open pit quarries are due to weathering, soil erosion, and the mass movement slope mechanisms [15, 27]. Based on reports, American mining surface fatality occurrence, slope instability accidents, is the first source of fatalities [12]. They explain: that it is critical for a final wall in open pit mining operations, and the failure is expensive to control and, at the same time, causes the loss of lives [23]. The open pit mines are getting deeper and deeper, where the recession risk is high [19]. As the open pit mines get larger and deeper, the slope design becomes more aggressive with the higher magnitude of the risk of failure and repercussions [30]. In the open pit slopes, the probability and amount of the material in the slope failure directly influence the potential impact [30]. Regardless of how minor a rockfall, which can drastically occur affects worker health, machinery capacity, and overall mine productivity [17]. The utilization of modern techniques in the testing of soil and rock stability analysis makes it possible to obtain a safe and economical design of quarry slopes [9]. Natural or engineered slope failures are mostly due to gravity. However, other factors, such as the strength of the rock, fracture strength, orientation, spacing, length of its discontinuities, pore pressure, geology, hydrology, surface conditions, and ground behavior, must also be considered [3]. The loosening of rock fragments and ore minerals left at the dump close to the mine site, which may be intensely fragmented and roundoff and can loosely race as surficial massive sheets upon rainfall saturation [28].

Opencast quarrying, the blasting and removal of overburden materials; rock and topsoil layers expose the mineral ore deposit below the earth's crust [4]. Blasting however does not get the ore ready for excavating and blasting is used to fracture the rock mass to come out in large blocks, which must then be split and separated into reasonable sizes like pieces. Opencast mining fractures the slope faces of the quarries, contributing to slope instability when it causes the slope to shift and accelerate. The method does not only consume land resources in the form of denudation of vegetation and topsoil fertility but also leads to soil crusting and erosion [13]. Surface mining activities convert opencast pits to high vertical heights of quarry slope faces, and expose the quarries to deformation and coercive failure [11]. The technique alters the overall slope angles as the practice is limited depending on the steep slope angles of the quarry walls [16]. Highwalls, for safety precautions, measure reports of geohazard warning signs; cracks, joints, hanging rocks, caved, gaping, slump/slippage, slide path race, and failure, concentrations [23, 29]. Other quarrying makes other slope falls susceptible to an impact [11]. Engineered lands with steeper slopes and do not practice soil management and engineering projects to construct buildings on steeper slopes have a much larger effect on slope instabilities [7]. Therefore, connecting slope instability problems in mining areas to unplanned opencast mining layouts makes sense [10].

Main Objective

The main objective of this analysis is to examine the role of mining safety and health regulations in monitoring and ensuring slope stability of mines in Kenya and Ghana and how to integrate and implement AI tools to promote the effectiveness and application of the regulations in the countries' mining sectors.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the slope stability of Kenyan and Ghanaian mines using the Limit Equilibrium numerical analysis method and geospatial statistics.
2. To establish the impact of mining designs and slope angles on quarry excavation slopes in the countries.
3. To evaluate mining statutes and regulations in Kenya Mining Act, Chapter 306 and Ghana Minerals and Mining Act 2006 Act 703 regarding slope stability, health, and safety regulations.
4. To optimize the capacity of AI tools for the implementation and application of slope stability monitoring, risk assessment, and decision-making in the Kenya and Ghana mining sectors.

5. To provide recommendations on how AI tools can be integrated into mine mining legal and regulatory frameworks to enhance the safety and health of workers and promote safe mining in Kenya and Ghana.

Justification for the Comparative Regulatory Analysis

A comparative regulatory analysis between the two countries is essential for several justifications.

1. Geological and environmental similarities: both Kenya and Ghana have similar geological formations and environmental conditions that affect the stability of the piles at their mining sites. A comparative analysis of how the regulatory frameworks of both countries address these common issues associated with mining sites and AI applications is thus a relevant analysis.
2. Regulations on mining health and safety: both Kenya and Ghana have regulatory frameworks that govern the mining sector and hence, the comparative analysis of the Mining Act of Kenya and Minerals and Mining of Ghana is important in understanding the comparison of the two tools.
3. Best practices comparison: by comparing the mining regulations in both countries, the researchers will identify best practices, lessons, and opportunities for the models' better use in the future.
4. Contribution to global development: mining regulations and the use of AI on mining site slopes is a global issue mostly affiliated with development objectives. Sustainable Growth Development Goals [SDGs] are a global concern of which SDGs 3, 8, and 9 work directly with the regulations and the site slopes, which means that this comparison provides helpful information on how Kenya and Ghana have and plan to align their practices with the global goals.

In sum, a comparative regulatory analysis between Kenya and Ghana is justified by the convergence of their countries' mining sectors, similar geological and environmental climates, regulatory frameworks for mining safety and health, the possibility for knowledge sharing and learning, and the input to a sustainable future. The information gathered from the analysis can be used to develop more effective and technology-driven approaches to slope stability management, as well as the improvement of sustainable and safe mining practices in both countries.

2.0 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF SLOPE ANALYSIS METHODS

I. Numerical limited equilibrium approaches

The most utilized procedures for assessing slope stability currently are limit equilibrium methods (LEMs). The fundamental premise of this category of methods is that mass failure involves a decline in which a mass slips over the slip plane [23]. The methods' reputation is high mostly due to their "simplicity," as well as their capacity to offer data on how sensitive the stability of the mass is to certain variables and the fact that geotechnical engineers have had years of experience assigning the safety factor to failure. According to the various limit equilibrium evaluation strategies, the failing soil mass is separated into several slices, and forces work on the slices, or different methods make different assumptions regarding the forces [23]. The LEMs are among the fundamental methods for studying slope stability. It is presumed that the mass is in balance between these polyhedral forces and that there is no issue with this analysis if the polyhedral forces are closed in the situation, and all presumptions and conditions are met. The basic premise of all of these approaches is to compare the stresses, moments, and resistance forces during motion with the tensions, moments, and denominations. [Equation (1)] [20]

$$Factor\ of\ Safety = \frac{\sum Resistance\ forces}{\sum Destructive\ Forces} .$$

The "Add Materials Boundary" function was utilized to separate the burden materials and rock layers. The software was given soil type along with its parameters such as soil turgidity, soil cohesion, and soil/phi based on soil and rock properties using the command "Define Materials". A circular form of slip was considered when estimating the circular slide's slope stability. The results were analyzed via graph visuals presenting slip surfaces. The safety factor determines the slope stability of the slope AFS of the special factors. If the safety factor is less than one, the research shows a very extreme risk of slope instability slide occurring. Should the safety factor range between one and one-quarter, then there is an apparent possibility of slope instability. If the safety factor ranges between two and five, the slope's propensity to geohazard is imperceptible [20, 32].

II. Types of Slope Failures

Slope instabilities and failures are common throughout the globe and may be triggered by a variety of reasons, including natural pressures, leading to substantial property and life losses. According to the type and nature of the structural control, rock slopes can be subdivided into several forms of collapse. Planar, wedge, toppling, and circular collapses are frequent occurrences in rock slopes. Rock slope stability is affected by four primary internal elements: geometry, the features of any potential failure planes, surface drainage, and the groundwater environment [24]. Rainfall, seismicity, and human-made activities are the primary external intervening variables.

The interaction of these variables determines the requirements for a slope to be stable. By assessing what measures can be taken against the variables that lead to slope instability, this study will present the steps that will ensure that the stability of the slopes can be enhanced. It also entails using different risk management strategies to counter the variables that would cause a slope to fail. The study of remediating slopes shall also include slopes modified by using the slope's geometry, drainage, and the use of retaining walls and internal slope strengthening [18]. Regarding the uncertainties concerning slope instability, this study will examine the risk management framework which is a hierarchical process that combines the identification of risks and therewith, the assessment and the control using varying methods. It is the correct identification of the risks and the extent of the risk that will help in identifying the most appropriate corrective measures that will lowly rectify the slump and landslide [18]. This study will involve the probabilities based on risk measures to reduce the likelihood of more slumping and landslides.

III. Frameworks for Mining Policies and Regulations

The mining regulations of the Mining Act of Kenya (Chapter 306) [2] and Ghana Minerals and Mining Act 2006 (Act 703) [1] provide legal guidelines that the mining operation should comply with to ensure that they perform their operation in a safe and sound environment.

Kenya's Mining Acts 2007, 2016, and 2017 have provisions on issues relating to the health, safety and protection of the environment that are applied in mining [2]. The legislation entrusts the Inspectorate Division under the Minerals Commission to ensure healthy standards of work, compliance with safety and health measures, conducting accident investigations and enforcing corrections. The Managers are responsible for the protection of workers by ensuring safe and healthy working systems, having safety materials and training and reporting accidents [1]. Besides, both legislations have set out regulations on the matters in slopes with measures preventing ground failures. The Mining (Safety) Regulations under the Mining Act, 2016 cover the duty of the mine owners and managers to maintain safe benches and pits, monitor the grounds, and report any failure or threat [2]. Minerals and Mining (Health, Safety and Technical) Regulations, 2012 (L.I. 2182) also covers the same issue of protection from ground failure [3]. Hence, with appropriate implementation and enforcement of these laws by responsible personnel, the incidences of accidents can be reduced, preventing loss and facilitating the sustainable mining of minerals. Slope stability can be enhanced under such provisions, especially in these countries, which experience challenges in contractions in the relative state of the ground of different altitudes. Therefore, using such measures as suitability and public safety can guarantee effective implementation and regulation.

IV Incorporating AI Tools in Mining

Incorporating Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in the mining sectors of Kenya and Ghana can significantly enhance the implementation, application, and effectiveness of safety and health regulations [26] [31], particularly in monitoring and maintaining slope stability. AI technologies offer advanced capabilities for data analysis, predictive modeling, and decision support, which can help mining companies and regulatory bodies to proactively identify and mitigate slope stability risks. The following aspects related to slope stability management can be realized with the usage of AI tools:

1. Data collection and integration: Algorithms can aggregate and standardize geotechnical, environmental, and operational inputs from different sources including sensors, monitoring systems, and databases. This approach will allow the generation of datasets for subsequent slope stability and risk analysis processes [8]. The same is relevant to other slope stability models.

2. Predictive modeling: Machine learning algorithms may be applied to existing slope stability data to develop models that forecast the probability of a slope failure in selected circumstances. The same applies to the design of different decision trees and supporting vector machine models and neural networks [5].
3. Real-time monitoring and early warning: AI-based tools can analyze results of monitoring exploitations and alert on instability signs if some results do not meet the expectancies [16]. The same is suitable for other monitoring techniques.
4. Risk assessment and decision support: Finally, AI and machine learning may be used for decision-making support based on the multiphase risk analysis [23].

The above mining laws and regulations within Kenya and Ghana form a legal framework that will facilitate the incorporation of AI tools in slope stability management. For instance, the Mining Act empowers the Commissioner of Mines and Geology to direct measurements for the safety of workings and the prevention of accidents [2]. Regulation 31 under the Mining Safety Regulations stipulates that it shall be the duty of the manager to see that sufficient safeguards are taken to ensure safe excavation and that danger from falls or slides is properly guarded against [2]. Such regulations, therefore, will create a platform for the integration of AI technologies to make slope stability monitoring and assessment more thorough. Similarly, Ghana's Minerals and Mining Act mandates the Inspectorate division under the Minerals Commission to enforce high health and safety standards for the mining industry [1]. According to Section 106 of the Act, it shall be the duty of all mine owners to take all reasonable measures to ensure that their mine is safe and for all persons working in mines to avoid accidents [1]. The Minerals and Mining Health, Safety, and Technical Regulations, 2012 further enhance these responsibilities [3]. Such legal provisions shall be utilized as avenues for implementing AI systems to enhance compliance with slope stability conditions. Several studies have shown the effectiveness of AI tools in slope stability management. For example, Bui et al. [8] developed a hybrid AI model that combined decision trees and evolutionary algorithms to predict slope failure in open-pit mines. The research achieved accuracies ranging from 79 to 93 percent in identifying potential failure zones. Kayusi et al. [16] utilized geospatial analysis and AI to assess slope stability in Kenyan quarries.

Therefore, the following steps are necessary to fully realize the benefits of AI in the mining sectors of Kenya and Ghana: first, developing guidelines and standards for the application of AI into slope stability management that would comply with the laws and regulations of mining on each country; second, capacity building of mining companies, regulatory bodies, and the workforce in AI technologies – such as training, workshops, and collaboration with scientific institutions; third, establishing data governance frameworks to ensure the quality, security and ethical use of data collected for the AI-based slope stability analysis; and fourth, creating an environment of innovation and improvement in the mining industry in general in which AI tools will be promoted to increase the safety and overall efficiency of the mining sector. Therefore, mining sectors in Kenya and Ghana can significantly enhance their implementation, application, and effectiveness of slope stability management using AI tools within current legal frameworks to prevent accidents, secure workers, and develop sustainable operations within both countries.

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Study Area

I. Geographic location

The study area is located in the mining regions of Kenya and Ghana, which host numerous mineral deposits. In Kenya, the most significant mining areas are the Rift Valley, Western, and Coastal regions while in Ghana – the country's mines are primarily situated in Ashanti, Western, Central and Eastern regions [16, 25].

II. Geological Setting

The geological background of the study areas consists of regional rock formations in which mineral resources are located. In Kenya, the most common rock types are the Archean Nyanzian System [16], the Proterozoic Mozambique Belt (graphite, titanium), and the Tertiary volcanic (diatomite, pozzolana). On the other hand, Ghana is mainly characterized by the Birimian Supergroup, Tarkwaian System and Voltaian Basin rock formations [1].

III. Climate

Kenya and Ghana have tropical climates that differ based on topography and proximity to water bodies. The former has hot and humid conditions in the coastal region and cold and wet conditions in the highlands. Kenya has a

bimodal rainfall pattern that includes long rains between March and May and short rains between October and December [16]. Ghana has hot and humid conditions distinguished by a heavy and light rainfall season; wet conditions from March to November and dry conditions from December to February. The annual rainfall for Ghana ranges between 1,000 mm in the north and 2,000 mm in the southwest [1].

IV. Methodology

The study used field observations and measurements, numerical modeling, AI tools, and regulatory and legal analysis. The quantitative measurements, such as the slope geometry parameters gathered from the sampled quarries, were entered into the Slide 6.0 software to perform Limit Equilibrium analyses. The software produced safety factors and generated a graphic representation of the slip surfaces [20]. AI tools like decision trees and evolution algorithms made slope failure predictions based on geotechnical and environmental data [8]. Geospatial data, GIS, and remote sensing were used to conduct a geospatial analysis of maps of the data [16]. The mining regulations for Kenya and Ghana were assessed on how they consider slope stability.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First, the Limit Equilibrium analyses performed with Slide 6.0 software showed that the stability of quarry slopes in both Kenya and Ghana is sensitive to the overall slope angles and the rock mass' strength properties [as depicted by Figures 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5]. A pattern of higher risk of failure was shown in steeper slopes and weak rock formations as shown in plates [a, b, c and d]; this is in line with the mining regulations of both countries, which allow for a safe angle of slope and ground failure. Under the Mining Act, Chapter 306 of the laws of Kenya, the Mining (Safety) Regulations regulate the design, operation, and maintenance of excavation pits [2]. Section 31 stated that the height and slope of the sides should be kept safe by the site's managers. In Ghana, the L.I. 2182, The Minerals and Mining (Health, Safety and Technical) Regulations, 2012 and Section 323 of the same Regulation stated that the angle of slope on the working field should be well designed and maintained [3]. The AI models developed in this study, based on decision trees and evolution algorithms, showed potential in predicting slope failure using different thematic maps obtained through a raster calculator. The models showed an accuracy of 80% to 95% in prediction, which makes it possible for use in the proactive identification of potential slope stability risks. These findings agree with the other literature sources, like the work of Bui et al., [8] who developed a hybrid AI model based on decision trees and evolutionary algorithms to predict slope failures in open-pit mines. Such a model had an accuracy of up to 93%.

[b] Soapstone Rock structure Discontinuities and Cracks

[c] Soapstone Boulders and Regolith Materials

[d] Abandoned Soapstone Quarry due to Slope Failure

Plates [a, b, c and d]. Show the geological characteristics of the Sameta Soapstone Quarry in Kisii County Kenya

Figure 1. Weathered Soapstone rocks at Sameta Quarry in Kisii County, Kenya

Figure 2. Diatomite Mine at Kariandusi in Nakuru County, Rift Valley Kenya

Figure 3. Limestone Quarry at Bofa Estate of the Northern Coast in Kilifi County, Kenya

Figure 4. Maso Quarry at Nsawam in the Eastern Region of Ghana

The stability of quarry slope is deduced by a stability index called the factor of safety, whereby Factor of Safety ≤ 1 indicating that the mine slopes are unstable and likely to fail, Factor of Safety = 1 implies the mine slopes are at equilibria state, and Factor of Safety ≥ 1 indicates that mine slopes are stable and safe for operations in shallow depths.

Figure 5. A Plot of Factor of Safety [FoS] Versus Slope Angle [°]

The factors of safety deduced for the four mines for a working slope height of 10 m are 0.55 for the weathered soapstone region at Sameta quarry in Kisii Kenya, 0.42 for the weathered limestone region in Bofa Estate Kilifi Kenya, 1.18 for the Diatomite mine in Kariandusi region, Nakuru Kenya and 1.21 for the Maso quarry region in Nsawam Ghana. According safety and regulations standards in [32], the safety factors for Sameta soapstone and Bofa limestone quarries are below the recommended slope safety factor of 1. While those of Diatomite Mine and Maso Quarry are above. An analysis of slope optimization conducted out shows that a higher factor of safety is maintained by minimizing the angles of quarry slopes. For instance, slope angle of 45° is optimum for Maso quarry, and 54° for Diatomite mine, while the overall slope angle of 74° for Bofa limestone quarry and 64° for Sameta soapstone quarry have safety factors below the recommended slope safety factor of 1. Slopes of Mines in both countries with greater heights require optimized slope angles to maintain the stability of the slopes for safety and sustainable mining operations.

The use of AI tools in slope stability management is in line with the mining regulations of Kenya and Ghana, which recommend the adoption of new technology to improve safety and avert accidents. Kenya Mining Act authorizes the Commissioner of Mines and Geology to issue such directions as he may consider necessary for the safety of workings and the prevention of accidents [2] [32]. Similarly, the Minerals and Mining Act, 2006 or Act 703 of Ghana requires the Inspectorate Division of Minerals Commission to promote health and safety standards of the mining industry [1]. Geospatial analysis conducted through GIS and remote sensing techniques, identified the various sources of incline instability, listening to the geological structures, groundwater states, and past and continuous mining activities. The finding demonstrates the need for intensifying geotechnical investigation and constant checks on incline conditions are expected in the mining regulations sphere of the two nations. Kenya's Mining requires that a manager's competence must be regularly examined by a qualified person who shall report any dangers and defects observed [2] and the same is in charge of Ghana's Minerals and Mining [3]. The comparative mining regulations of Kenya and Ghana confirm that the slope pattern, testing, and management set by the provision are vital in promoting safety and preventing accidents. Thus, both Mining Acts provide a solid foundation for integrating AI tools in slope stability management. For instance, data from AI-based monitoring surveillance can be used to prove compliance with the regulation, such as retaining secure slope inclination and taking corrective actions or necessary.

Additionally, AI tools can improve the efficiency of risk assessment and decision-making processes related to slope instability management. By scrutinizing the real-time data obtained from monitoring devices and databases with information on slope performance over the years, AI algorithms can extrapolate failure patterns and triggers as well as the optimal ways to mitigate them. This is in line with the underlying principles of the risk-based approach stipulated by the mining legislation which presupposes the necessity to identify, evaluate, and control workplace hazards to protect employees' safety and health as described in the relevant legal acts of Kenya and Ghana [1, 2]. The results of this study signal the necessity of developing active collaboration between mining companies, regulatory bodies, and research institutions to realize the full potential of AI in slope instability management. Policy

development to regulate AI use, education and training, the development of data policies and procedures, and the promotion of innovative business culture are the critical areas to focus on. Given that both Kenyan and Ghanaian mining legislation promote collaborative rather than adversarial frameworks that emphasize continuous improvement and the search for the best ways to secure safety and health [1, 2], the countries' legal systems create favorable conditions to implement these findings. Moreover, the findings of the current study suggest that it is worthwhile combining AI tools with traditional geotechnical engineering methods and regulatory compliance. Limit Equilibrium analysis and AI modeling, in combination with geological and engineering visualization tools and regulatory compliance, can help to create a comprehensive and proactive approach to slope instability. This also corresponds with the principles of responsible and sustainable mining that are progressively addressed in Kenyan and Ghanaian law [1, 2].

To summarize, the findings and analysis presented and discussed in this study underscore the importance of mining safety and health regulations concerning monitoring and maintaining slope stability in the mines of Kenya and Ghana. The case studies involving Limit Equilibrium analysis, AI modeling, and geospatial analysis offer valuable insights into the various influence factors pertaining to slope stability, and the potential of AI applications in aiding risk assessment and decision-making. The implementation of AI technology into the legal systems of Kenya and Ghana could facilitate the practical application and efficiency of slope stability management practices. Therefore, the use of AI would be instrumental in ensuring the prevention of accidents, workers' safety, and sustainable mining in general. The evidence and analysis in this study emphasize the need for a coordinated and proactive approach involving miners, mining companies, and regulatory authorities. Through the laws and regulations of these countries, the implementation of AI technologies and a culture of continuous improvement, miners in Kenya and Ghana can address the challenges of slope stability and worker safety. Finally, this study has contributed to the knowledge of the application of AI in the mining field especially mining in developing countries, and the successful use of AI in slope stability could be applied to mining environmental monitoring and resource optimization.

However, it is critical to recognize the limitations and issues related to AI implementation in Kenya and Ghana's mining sectors. Such considerations might pertain to the adequacy and reliability of the data, the levels of expertise for creating and maintaining AI systems, and the overall investment. Such aspects require serious transformations across all groups involved in the process, including the relevant authorities, industry groups, and educational organizations. These actors must work together to institute the suitable infrastructure, knowledge, and capital to efficiently deal with the expectations of AI use. Additionally, the ethical and social considerations of AI applications in the mining industry need to be carefully studied. Concerns regarding data protection, algorithmic discrimination, and job loss should be tackled through the formulation of legislation, rules, and preventive measures. Mining policies and rules in Kenya and Ghana should be developed to allow the responsible and ethical usage of AI tools, with the advantages justly appropriated and the employees and communities protected.

To conclude, drawing from the outcomes as well as the arguments of this research, the potential implementation of AI tools to promote sustainable grade management in Kenya and Ghana's mining sectors maintains the existing rule and policy models. The paper recalls the vast influence of a consolidated, active, and ethical AI use approach as driven by healthy and sustainability concepts. By seizing the potential provided by AI tools while tackling the difficulties and consequences, Kenya and Ghana's mining sectors are likely to pave the way for a safer, more productive, and sustainable future.

1. Conduct comprehensive geotechnical investigations and stability analyses during the planning and design stages to determine safe slope angles and support requirements [16].
2. Implement slope monitoring using a combination of conventional methods such as survey prisms, inclinometers and modern technologies such as radar, LiDAR, and satellite InSAR to indicate any deformations and signs of instability [8].
3. Utilize appropriate slope reinforcement methods, such as rock bolting, cable anchoring, shotcreting, and drainage systems, to improve the stability of the critical slopes [18].
4. Develop and preserve a database of slope performance, including geotechnical parameters, monitoring data, and incidents of failure to support informed decision-making and risk assessment [23].
5. Train the workforce regularly on slope stability hazards, safe work practices, and emergency rescue or escape procedures [1, 2].
6. Improve the capacity of the regulatory bodies, such as Kenya's Mines and Geology Department and Ghana's Inspectorate Division of the Minerals Commission, to monitor, inspect, and enforce slope stability laws [1, 2].
7. Facilitate cooperation and knowledge sharing among mining companies, research organizations, and governments to address the slope stability problem with innovative solutions [16].

8. Incorporate AI technologies and machine learning tools in the slope stability management workflow to enhance failure prediction capability, improve monitoring policies, and aid in risk-informed decision-making [8].

Implementing these recommendations and continuously enhancing slope stability practices will improve that record in both Kenya and Ghana.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This study has provided a wide range of information on the role of mining safety and health regulations in monitoring and maintaining slope stability in the Kenyan and Ghanaian mines, particularly considering the incorporation and usage of Artificial Intelligence tools. The results and discussions have shown the importance of geotechnical factors, mining practices, and regulatory frameworks in the stability of the slopes and the possibility of accidents. The deformation analyses, AI, geotechnical modeling, and a geospatial arrangement provide much understanding of what causes anomalies in the slope and how AI tools can help improve the robustness of assessing risks and taking decisions on the same. Their mining laws and regulation safety aspects, such as those of Kenya and Ghana in the Mining Act, Chapter 306 and Minerals and Mining Act of 2006 Act 703 respectively, justice attire to the safety management methods and inclusion of high technological equipment. These acts urge it is safe to maintain safe slope angles and ensure regular inspection for curative actions to prevent incidences of failures on the ground. The inclusion of AI tools in these regulations may foster much help to the safety of slope stability. Nonetheless, the current application of AI in the mining fields of Kenya and Ghana draws some limitations. They include comprehensive data collection, capacity strengthening to adhere to the usage of AI technologies, making guidelines and standards for the safe use of AI, and ethical and social benefits. The limitations require the mining companies, regulators, and research institutions and other involved stakeholders to adhere to facilitate the responsible use of AI.

Following the findings of this study, the subsequent recommendations are made to protect worker health and safety in mines and maximize the use of AI tools in slope stability control:

1. Intensify compliance with and adherence to mining health and safety legislation as it relates to slopes, including by increasing the frequency of inspections, audits, and penalties for non-compliance.
2. Boost the deployment of AI tools in the monitoring and risk assessment of slope stability by providing mining firms and regulatory agencies with incentives, technical assistance, and ability creation programs.
3. Create comprehensive AI application guidelines and standards for AI application in slope stability control that follow Kenyan and Ghanaian mining regulations to help prevent and improve AI outcomes.
4. Increase cooperation and data exchange among mining firms, academic institutions, and government bodies to introduce and approve proven and effective AI strategies for controlling slope stability.
5. Investing in the education of knowledgeable personnel in AI skills through instruction, academic curriculum, and expertise-building schemes to acquire AI knowledge.
6. Develop and introduce data framework policies and strategies to assure the quality, safety, and ethical usage of AI considerations purchased and maintained while adhering to appropriate legislation.
7. Perform regular risk assessments and certification of AI systems application in slope stability control to assist in addressing or decreasing the impact of potential biases, mistakes, or problems' results.
8. Encounter a safety, accountability, and openness culture in the sector by unifying the reporting process on slope fall-produced accidents, warnings, and measures to be implemented.
9. Engage with local communities, workers' unions, and other stakeholders to raise awareness about the benefits and risks of AI in mining, and ensure that the adoption of AI tools is inclusive, equitable, and responsive to societal concerns.

10. Continuously review and update the mining laws and regulations in Kenya and Ghana to keep pace with the rapid advancements in AI technologies, ensuring that the legal frameworks remain relevant, effective, and adaptive to emerging challenges and opportunities.

Implementation of these recommendations and the use of the power of AI tools within the strong legislative and regulatory systems of Kenya and Ghana will allow both countries to significantly improve worker safety and health, reduce the risks of slope failures, and support the sustainable growth of the mining industry. AI implementation in slope stability management, approved by appropriate legislation, is poised to change the mining business and regulation in the areas of risk assessment, decision-making, and incident prevention. However, it is important to note that the successful implementation of AI in the mining sectors in Kenya and Ghana is a long and collaborative process that requires continuous commitment, investment, and collaboration of all parties involved. Combining the effort, the industry players and the law will be able to move toward safer, more efficient, and sustainable mining powered by AI.

In conclusion, this study has revealed the high promise of using AI tools to improve management practices concerning slope stability and workers' health and safety in Kenyan and Ghanaian mines. With AI assistance complementing comprehensive legislative and regulatory measures in both countries' mining segments, it will become possible to address the issues with slope instabilities, reducing the number of accidents, and advancing the concepts of corporate social responsibility and sustainability. The recommendations provided in this paper can serve as a guideline for appropriately integrating AI tools into the practice of slope stability maintenance. Therefore, the application of the methods mentioned here can facilitate safer, more productive, and sustainable mining perspectives in Kenya and Ghana.

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